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The conference will be organized in a HYBRID way, which will allow for both physical and online participation of the attendees.

The global economy of the twenty-first century has transformed the economic, social, and political landscape in a profound way. This century has been the scene of revolutions in information and communication technologies, enhanced economic integrations with capital mobility across readers, and a rapidly changing social environment.

In this context, **IRCOBESS 2024**'s main theme is “*New Approaches in Economics and Business: Problems & Opportunities*”. In accordance with this, we welcome studies in the fields of economics and business management; also, in branches of social sciences such as public administration, politics, regional studies, and international studies that are related to economics and business management. Studies that are not within the scope of the conference will not be evaluated.

The aim of the conference is to gather leading academicians, policymakers, independent scholars, and researchers to share their knowledge, and new ideas as well as to discuss future development in these fields. It also provides a premier interdisciplinary platform for researchers, practitioners, and educators to present and discuss the most recent innovations, trends, and concerns as well as practical challenges encountered and solutions adopted in the fields of Economics, Business, and Social Sciences.

An additional goal of the **IRCOBESS 2024** is to offer an opportunity for young researchers, academicians, and practitioners with multidisciplinary interests to meet and interact with members inside and outside their own particular disciplines.

PRACTICAL STEPS TOWARDS THE ESTABLISHMENT OF A COMPULSORY HEALTH INSURANCE SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Uzbekistan is continuing the gradual implementation of the compulsory health insurance (CHI) system, which aims to improve the availability and quality of medical services for citizens. The study examines the key steps and financial mechanisms required for the effective implementation of CHI, including legislative support, the establishment of a national body, the formation of a package of services and pricing. International practices and characteristics of adapting the system to local conditions are considered. Recommendations are made to improve the financing and availability of medical services and to ensure the sustainability of the system. The introduction of CHI in Uzbekistan contributes to the improvement of health care, financial security for citizens and equal access to medical services.

KEY WORDS

State health insurance, public-private partnership, availability of medical services, quality of medical care, compulsory health insurance, health care reforms, Uzbekistan, financing of the health care system, stages of implementation.

INTRODUCTION

Recent health reforms in Uzbekistan aimed at improving health service delivery and accessibility are key to the successful implementation of the compulsory health insurance (CHI) system. These reforms should focus on improving the quality of health care, expanding access to services, and allocating resources efficiently. It is important that the reforms are consistent with the objectives of the CHI, ensuring universal coverage and sustainable financing that contributes to improving the health system and citizens' access to necessary health services.

The gradual implementation of state health insurance mechanisms in medical institutions in Tashkent began on 1 January 2024. This is provided for in the presidential decree on the implementation of the Uzbekistan 2030 strategy issued this year.

The health insurance scheme provides for the introduction of a state-guaranteed volume of free medical services and a list of medicines by disease group. The September presidential decree set the end of 2026 as the completion date for the implementation of health insurance in Uzbekistan. From 2024, the State Health Insurance Fund will be incorporated into the structure of the Ministry of Health, and from 2027 it will become an independent fund [1,2,9].

Scientific novelty. The study is an overview of integrated approaches to the creation of the compulsory health insurance system in Uzbekistan, based on current reforms, international achievements in this area and an analysis of the characteristics of the national health system. It presents the development of a step-by-step plan and analysis of the practical steps necessary for the successful implementation of compulsory health insurance, taking into account local conditions, national priorities and the strategic objectives of the Uzbekistan 2030 programme.

It also proposes solutions for optimal resource allocation and sustainable financing of the health system, based on international experience and current realities in Uzbekistan.

Research objective: Identification of effective practical steps and development of an algorithm for the implementation of the compulsory health insurance system in Uzbekistan, contributing to the improvement of the availability and quality of medical services, as well as the sustainability of the health care financing system.

The objectives of the study were to examine the issues of financial resources of the state compulsory medical insurance system in Uzbekistan, the potential for the development of the compulsory medical insurance system, a comparative assessment with the world experience, a study of the features of the implementation of the compulsory medical insurance system in Uzbekistan, as well as the development of an integrated approach with the consistent implementation of key steps to the implementation of the compulsory medical insurance system in Uzbekistan.

Research methods. In the process of collecting, processing and analyzing research materials, using modern scientific publications both in Uzbekistan and abroad, a comprehensive approach with consistent implementation of key steps for more effective implementation of the compulsory health insurance system in Uzbekistan was developed.

The financial resources of the State Compulsory Medical Insurance Scheme in Uzbekistan are formed by contributions from policyholders, which are the main source of funding.

These funds are used to implement state policy in the field of compulsory medical insurance, to ensure the sustainable functioning of the system and the availability of medical services to the population.

In most countries with a developed compulsory health insurance system, there are three main sources of funding for this fund:

Budget contributions – funds allocated by the state to ensure the functioning of the health insurance system and to cover the cost of medical services for citizens.

Employers' funds – contributions from employers who are required to contribute to the health insurance of their employees.

Personal funds from citizens – contributions from citizens themselves, who participate in the compulsory health insurance system and pay part of the cost of medical services.

These sources make it possible to create a financially sustainable system that ensures the availability and quality of medical care for all segments of the population.

Uzbekistan's national compulsory health insurance system provides equal access to health services and financial protection for citizens, and is funded by the national budget and contributions from employers and employees. It supports small and medium-sized enterprises, which contributes to economic development. Opportunities for improvement include the development of voluntary and compulsory insurance and social protection reforms to improve access to health care [2,3,5].

Resources and development potential of the compulsory health insurance system The compulsory health insurance system in Uzbekistan is regulated by specific laws and regulations that define its scope and mechanisms of operation. These laws aim to ensure the availability and accessibility of medical services for all citizens. The funds of the state compulsory health insurance system in Uzbekistan are formed from employers' contributions and compulsory insurance for uninsured citizens, and are also supported by the state budget in order to expand access to medical services. Social funds play an important role in income redistribution, taking into account the national characteristics of the economy [2,10]. Current research is aimed at improving the organization and financing of the social protection system, with particular attention being paid to the development of voluntary and compulsory health insurance, improving the procedures for paying unemployment benefits and ensuring the stability of the pension system (Table 1). Recent reforms include the updating of pension procedures, the introduction of legislation on compulsory health insurance and the adoption of the "Law on Social Insurance", which aims to strengthen the social protection of certain groups. The system is part of a broader social insurance system that includes other forms of social protection such as pensions and unemployment benefits, underlining its role in the country's social security system [5]. Comparison with international experience. The analysis of international models of health care financing shows that no country has a transparent or perfectly designed model and that, as a rule, one source of financing accounts for more than 70% of public expenditure, indicating a dependence on budgetary and insurance models.

This underlines the difficulties of providing comprehensive health care funding exclusively from public sources. A comparative assessment of the compulsory health insurance system in Uzbekistan can be made according to the following main criteria: financing, availability and quality of medical services, participation of the private sector and social guarantees for citizens. Comparing Uzbekistan's compulsory health insurance system with similar systems in other countries, it is possible to identify both common and unique features [2,8].

Uzbekistan's compulsory health insurance system is financed by contributions from insurers, including government funds and employer contributions. Uzbekistan is implementing a step-by-step approach to establishing a compulsory health insurance scheme, starting with individual regions, which allows the policy to be adapted according to regional characteristics and needs. In countries with a developed compulsory health insurance system (such as Germany or Japan), the health insurance fund is formed from three sources: the state budget, employer funds and personal contributions from citizens. This allows the financial burden to be shared and increases the sustainability of the system. In Uzbekistan, the financing system is still in its infancy, and further development may include attracting additional sources, such as personal contributions from citizens [8,10].

Table 1.

Share of insurance payments made in the voluntary health insurance market of Uzbekistan in relation to collected insurance premiums.

Years	Insurance premiums (billion soums)	Insurance payments (billion soums)	Ratio of insurance payments to insurance premiums (in %)	Last year: relative increase (+) or decrease (-) (in %)
2018	9,3	7,3	78,5	0,7
2019	18,0	10,7	59,4	-18,4
2020	19,5	11,4	58,5	-0,9
2021	23,9	15,4	64,4	6,1
2022	28,4	20,5	72,2	6,8

In Uzbekistan, the gradual introduction of compulsory health insurance aims to improve the availability of basic health services, such as emergency care, consultations, vaccinations and tests, financed by the state.

The compulsory health insurance fund directs funds to institutions that provide quality services and also develops quality control, staff training and infrastructure modernization [1]. Uzbekistan intends to gradually eliminate differences between public and private clinics to ensure equal quality of health services. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) play an important role in attracting private investment and expertise. In countries with a developed system of compulsory health insurance, the private sector is often actively involved in the provision of health services, expanding opportunities for citizens and improving the competitive environment. In the Netherlands and Switzerland, for example, health insurance companies operate independently, allowing patients to choose from a wide range of private and public providers [4].

Features of the implementation of the compulsory health insurance system in Uzbekistan The compulsory health insurance system in Uzbekistan is being gradually implemented, expanding the range of services and the financial autonomy of medical institutions. Unlike developed systems, it adapts to local conditions and requires new financing mechanisms, standardization of the per capita budget and a system of contracts to ensure free medical care. Compulsory health insurance supports economic stability and protects businesses and citizens. The introduction of social insurance and adaptation to international standards provide opportunities to improve access to health care and financial protection, but require consideration of the economic conditions and needs of the population [3,6,8].

A pilot project to introduce national health insurance (NHI) in Uzbekistan was launched in July 2021 in the Syrdarya region, with the aim of improving the provision of and access to health services. The project is based on the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO) and covers two key areas of reform: the financing system and the health care delivery system [2,7].

1. Financing system: moving from financing infrastructure (e.g. beds and utilities) to paying for the actual medical services provided to patients.

This means that funds are now directed towards paying for medical services that a specific person needs.

2. Health care delivery system: changes in clinical practice to focus on the outcomes of medical services rather than the treatment process, and improving the availability of these services to the population. The pilot has shown good results in these areas.

The project created a free package of medical services financed from the state budget through the State Health Insurance Fund (SHIF), which purchases services from medical institutions. The SHI Fund acts as an intermediary, transferring funds directly to the institutions' accounts, thereby ensuring their financial independence. With improved management skills, medical institutions will be given more autonomy, which will eventually allow equal access to quality services in public and private clinics.

The guaranteed free package includes

Ambulance and hospitalization in emergencies;

Appointments with general practitioners and specialist consultations;

Laboratory tests and diagnostic studies ordered by a family doctor;

Screening examinations and vaccinations according to the national immunization calendar;

Outpatient treatment, medical rehabilitation and palliative care;

Purchase of medicines from the list approved by the Ministry of Health.

A reimbursement system will also be introduced, which will allow patients to receive medicines free of charge according to electronic prescriptions issued by a family doctor. The results of the pilot project in the Syrdarya region will serve as a basis for further expanding access to guaranteed, high-quality health care in other regions of Uzbekistan, using a new model of health care organization.

In order to expand access to quality medical services, a phased process of introducing compulsory health insurance in the Navoi region will begin on 1 January 2023. Then, from 1 October 2023, the project was extended to the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the city of Tashkent.

Since 1 January 2024, the implementation of compulsory health insurance has continued in the Samarkand, Surkhandarya and Fergana regions. These measures are aimed at providing citizens with more accessible and higher quality healthcare, improving healthcare financing and increasing the efficiency of healthcare delivery [7].

A comprehensive approach with consistent implementation of key steps will be required to successfully establish a compulsory health insurance system in Uzbekistan:

1. Development of the legal framework

Development of the legal framework for the compulsory health insurance system: development and adoption of laws that define the basic concepts, objectives and functions of the compulsory health insurance system, as well as the obligations of citizens and employers.

Establishing the rules for the operation of the compulsory health insurance system: drafting regulations for the detailed regulation of the process of providing medical services, the calculation of tariffs and the rules for the operation of the compulsory health insurance fund.

Establishing regulatory and control mechanisms: Establishing mechanisms for state control over the activities of the compulsory health insurance system to ensure transparency, respect for citizens' rights and accountability.

2. Establishment of a national compulsory health insurance body

Establishment of the organizational structure: creation of a central compulsory health insurance fund with regional branches that will manage the programme on the ground and interact with local medical institutions.

Definition of roles and responsibilities: distribution of roles and responsibilities between central and regional units, definition of responsibilities for collection of contributions, purchasing of medical services and accounting.

Appointment of management and key specialists: Selection of competent management responsible for strategic planning and financial management, as well as key specialists in IT, monitoring and financial management.

3. Defining the package of services and tariffs

Developing a basic package of medical services: defining the list of services included in the guaranteed package based on the priorities of the health system and the needs of the population.

Calculate tariffs based on cost analysis: establish economically sound tariffs that take into account the cost of medical services and maintain the availability of medical care.

Coordinating the service package and tariffs with stakeholders: consulting with medical institutions, employers and the public to take into account the interests of all parties.

4. Setting up a contribution collection system

Establish mechanisms for collecting insurance contributions: develop a convenient and efficient system that takes into account deductions from employers and possibly citizens.

Establishing a database of insured persons: Establishing a single register of compulsory health insurance participants with up-to-date data on each citizen, including insurance status and entitlement to medical services.

Ensuring reliable collection and accounting of revenues: developing mechanisms for timely and accurate accounting of contributions, preventing arrears and automating the collection process.

5. Development of IT system infrastructure

Implementation of information systems for the management of compulsory health insurance: development or purchase of IT systems to automate fund management, accounting of insurance premiums and expenses.

Creation of an integrated database of insured persons and services provided: creation of a database for registering patients, recording services provided and collecting statistics.

Ensuring data protection and confidentiality: implementing security standards to protect personal data and prevent leaks.

6. Pilot implementation in different regions

Selection of pilot regions according to regional characteristics: Identification of regions for testing the system, taking into account their economic, demographic and medical characteristics.

Development of mechanisms for interaction between participants in the compulsory health insurance system: Establishment of interaction processes between the compulsory health insurance fund and medical institutions, employers and citizens.

Analysis of pilot results and adaptation of approaches: evaluation of the effectiveness of the system in the pilot regions, identification of problem areas and changes in the operating models of the compulsory health insurance.

7. Gradual expansion throughout the country

Gradual expansion of the compulsory health insurance system to other regions: gradually connecting new regions and ensuring gradual adaptation of the system.

Monitoring and troubleshooting: continuous monitoring of implementation results, audits and prompt response to emerging problems.

8. Integration with the health system

Coordinating the work of the compulsory health insurance system with existing medical institutions: ensuring cooperation between the compulsory health insurance system and public and private medical institutions, establishing service standards.

Optimizing patient flow and financial resources: adjusting the patient flow system to balance the workload between institutions and optimizing funding.

Improving the quality and availability of medical services: using monitoring to ensure high quality standards, promptly resolving emerging problems with availability.

9. Continuous monitoring and improvement

Assessing the effectiveness of the compulsory health insurance system: regular data collection, analysis of indicators and preparation of reports on the quality and availability of medical care.

Making the necessary changes and improving the mechanisms: continuously adapting and optimising working methods, ensuring that they are in line with the objectives of the system and the needs of the population.

Ensuring the financial sustainability of the system: monitoring financial indicators, preventing deficits and, if necessary, attracting additional sources of funding.

These steps will create the basis for the full and sustainable functioning of the compulsory health insurance system in Uzbekistan, ensuring access to medical services for all citizens and improving the level of health care.

The study of key aspects of the implementation of compulsory health insurance in Uzbekistan, including financing, development of the system and its features, allowed for a comparative analysis with international experience. Based on the data and scientific publications, a comprehensive approach was developed, including measures for distribution of funds, strategic planning and adaptation of international practices to local conditions. Recommendations were formulated for the integration of compulsory health insurance to improve the availability of medical services and the financial sustainability of health care. The findings can serve as a basis for a national strategy for the development of compulsory health insurance in Uzbekistan.

Conclusions:

1. The financial sustainability of the compulsory health insurance system in Uzbekistan is achieved through mixed financing from the budget, employer contributions and citizens' personal funds. However, further strengthening of the system will require legislative changes aimed at attracting additional sources of financing, including citizen contributions.

2. The role of compulsory health insurance in improving the availability and quality of medical services is important for the social protection of the population. The introduction of a basic package of free services increases availability and promotes an equitable distribution of medical resources.
3. Comparison with international models reveals common and unique elements specific to Uzbekistan, suggesting the possibility of borrowing successful practices, such as standardization of service quality and involvement of the private sector, to improve competitiveness and accessibility of medical care.

4. Pilot projects of compulsory health insurance in the regions demonstrate the success of a step-by-step approach, which makes it possible to adapt the system implementation process and take into account local specificities.

Recommendations. It is necessary to strengthen the legal framework of the compulsory health insurance system, as well as to control the implementation and transparency of financial flows. The creation of a central compulsory health insurance fund with regional branches will facilitate more efficient financial management and coordination of services provided by medical institutions and partners. The introduction of an information system and database for the registration of insured persons and services received will ensure reliable storage and protection of personal data.

Suggestions. It is necessary to extend pilot projects for the introduction of compulsory medical insurance to new regions, gradually covering the whole country, with analysis and adjustments after each stage to improve efficiency and meet the needs of the local population. Include private medical institutions in the compulsory medical insurance system with the possibility of equal provision of medical services, develop public-private partnerships and stimulate competition. It is important to improve the mechanism for financing medical institutions based on the principle of payment for services actually rendered, directing funds to effective medical procedures and optimizing patient routing.

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